

FORMATION OF BUSINESS MODELS AND DEVELOPMENT OF CORPORATE KARTING AS AN ENTERTAINMENT AND SPORTS INDUSTRY

Chaldanbayev Y.

Doctoral Candidate, DBA Program,

Kazakh-British Technical University (KBTU), Almaty, Republic of Kazakhstan

Abstract

Today, corporate karting is not only a popular place for visitors, but also a profitable business for entrepreneurs who decide to take up this business. Almost every city in a developed country around the world has various karting organizations and tracks equipped with the necessary infrastructure, since the demand for this sport in foreign countries is quite high.

Keywords: corporate karting, infrastructure.

1. Introduction

Karting is a sport and entertainment, kart racing - the simplest racing cars without a body and, most often, with open wheels. The speed of the kart (Superkart class) can reach 260 km/h.

It is believed that karting was invented by military pilots in the United States after World War II. They arranged races around the airfield on trolleys for transporting aerial bombs. But this hobby was only spread in narrow circles, until Art Ingles, a former pilot, mechanic of the Glendale branch of the Curtis Craft Company, which produced racing cars, took over. In August 1956, at the Pomona motor race, he presented to the public a simple kart. The car was called a trolley (in english *cart*).

In 1957, Bill Rowles, Duffy Livingstone, and Roy Desbrow form the Go-Kart Company, a kart company. The company was doing so well that it was able to buy a 5-acre plot on which the first karting track was built. At the same time, Ingles founds the Ingels-Borelli company. In 1958, English businessman Mickey Flynn orders five karts from Go-Kart. As early as 1960, there were over 100 companies in the UK producing cards and components.

Kart, due to its small mass, was often used to break speed records on cars with a small engine, as well as for experiments with unusual power plants. There are several attempts to install a jet engine on the kart, the highest recorded speed is 407 km / h. The German physicist and power engineer Laing built a steam-powered kart to demonstrate how compact and reliable such a power plant could be.

The cards of those years were distinguished by a very simple design, low engine power and the complete absence of any security measures. The price of such a card ranged from 100 to 200 US dollars.

It was thanks to the simplicity and cheapness that karting gained wild popularity in the early years of its existence. But by 1962, the karting boom was over. The number of manufacturing firms has fallen. Cards have become more powerful and more perfect, but also more

expensive. The simplest frames made of water pipes were replaced by structures with carefully calculated elasticity. Increasing speeds required increased safety. As in any other technical sport, professionals remained in karting.

2. Materials and methods

Karting is usually divided into sports and amateur (or rental).

Sports karting, in turn, is professional, which is based on the activities of a professional sports organization and infrastructure.

In May 1960, the International Motor Sports Federation officially recognized karting as a form of motor sport. In 1962, the International Karting Commission of the International Motorsport Federation (CIK FIA) was established. The International Karting Commission (French: Commission Internationale de Karting, abbr. CIK, CIK-FIA) is the main international sanctioning body for karting.

The Commission is active in the development of karting throughout the world and the regulation of existing karting competitions. The most significant CIK tournament is the World Karting Championship.

The Karting World Championship is a karting competition organized by the CIK - FIA. It has been held annually since 1964 and is the flagship event in karting. The FIA (International Automobile Federation) created the CIK (International Karting Commission) in 1962.

The FIA is best known to the general public as the governing body for motor racing. In 1922, the federation transferred the organization of motor racing to the CSI (Commission Sportive Internationale), an independent committee, which later became known as FISA (Fédération Internationale du Sport Automobile, FISA). The restructuring of the FIA in 1993 led to the disappearance of FISA, placing auto racing under the direct control of the FIA [1].

The FIA General Assembly is the highest governing body, made up of the presidents of the numerous FIA member clubs (Table 1).

Table 1.

Structure of the FIA (FIA) - International Automobile Federation

FIA General Assembly:	
-The President of the FIA also serves as Chairman of the General Assembly:	
➤ <input type="checkbox"/> Deputy President for Mobility and Vehicles:	➤ <input type="checkbox"/> Deputy President for Sports:

1. FIA World Council on Mobility and Motor Vehicles - governs all non-sporting activities of the FIA	2. Commission on motor vehicles and cars	1. FIA World Council of Motorsport - governs all sporting events regulated by the FIA	2. Sports commissions.
– FIA Senate			
– FIA International Court of Appeal			
– FIA Secretariat			

Source: <https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki>

There is also a rental or amateur type of this type of motorsport. The rental type of leisure is quite safe and even people with no driving experience are invited to the track. There are even children's karting schools and children's cards. Amateur karting does not require special clothing.

Now in Europe this type of entertainment is very popular and loved. Due to its low cost, car rental in kart clubs is available to almost everyone.

Sport has long turned into a huge business industry - primarily entertainment, albeit with a huge positive impact on a healthy lifestyle.

Gran karting club on the island of Gran Canaria is one of the best European clubs. Anyone can get acquainted here with the basics of kart control, study the design of the machine. The track of the club has a length of 1650 m, and models of cars are capable of speeds up to 100 km/h. For children, the club has a special area where, under the guidance of experienced instructors, they can learn the basics of karting. For teenagers under 16 there is a Junior track.

The Gran Karting club was founded in 1983 and to this day is the benchmark in the world of karting and motorsport in the Canary Islands. Our facilities hosted the Spanish Karting Championships, the Canary Islands Karting Championships, and as a showcase venue for the European Rally Championship.

The club has always wanted to evolve and adapt, which is why the club's facilities are ideal for adults and children, offering the best safety measures on the track and the best rental karts on the market. For the club, the safety of its customers is the most important thing, adapting each track to its users according to their age.

Recently, more and more major global companies and brands have been investing in motorsport to promote themselves and idealize their image (Kaspersky Lab, Coca Cola, Monster Energy, Red Bull, Amazon, Ebay, Ray Ban, BWT and others). Company managers and management in particular are interested in the development of this investment segment, as it allows you to show the company from the side of an active player and leader with global ambitions.

Many companies are looking for an opportunity for a bright and presentable entry into the global business arena, which actually makes it possible to make the Nürburgring Mecca of motorsport with participation in cult sporting events. Nürburgring (Nürburgring, hereinafter simply Ring) is without a doubt the most famous race track in the world. The Nordschleife track was designed and built from 1925 to 1927.

The Nürburgring GP track for Formula 1 was put into operation in 1984. The length of the route is 5.148 km. Number of turns -15. The track record belongs to

Michael Schumacher, who in 2004 drove a full GP lap in a Formula car in 1:29.468 minutes.

Thus, the Nürburgring complex now includes several race tracks: the legendary Nordschleife with a length of 20.8 km and the more standard GP Strecke with a length of 5.1 km. It is curious that during the iconic racing marathons Nürburgring Endurance Series and 24 Hours of Nürburgring, these tracks combine to form the most unique track configuration on the Ring. For free rides on tourist days, most amateurs use the Nordschleife track (20.8 km) exclusively. GP - the track can also be used for races, but much less often [2].

Currently, in large cities of the Republic of Kazakhstan, there are rental karting sites, intended mainly for entertainment. In rental karting, chassis with box-less low-power engines are used. The pilot does not need any special training to operate such a kart.

In addition, there is a so-called "winter karting" in the Republic of Kazakhstan. Competitions in this sport are held on snow and ice. Special tires are used both with and without studs. The chassis, depending on the class, are equipped with engines from 50 to 250 cc. cm.

The karting track STK "Sokol" is located in the Almaty region. This is a track that has no analogues in Kazakhstan, the total length of the track is 1650 meters. The track consists of a variety of turns, a straight line and a pit lane, all results are recorded by the most accurate telemetry system. Children's races are held separately.

3. Results and conclusions

Whether recreational or rental, karting develops more as an entrepreneurial activity and is based on a business model. A business model is an analysis and a schematic description of the interrelated business processes of a company. The model clearly shows: what, to whom and how exactly to sell, as well as how profitable it is.

This is not an in-depth business study, but rather an express analysis that allows you to understand:

- how to develop the company;
- how to optimize business processes;

What resources do you need to attract to grow your business?

The business model helps startups to evaluate a niche, see prospects and hidden risks, and test ideas. For an existing business - to find weaknesses and points of growth in order to adjust its work.

The most popular template of the business model of an enterprise (Business Model Canvas) was developed by Alexander Osterwalder and Yves Pigneur [3]. It consists of 9 blocks - key elements of the business (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Business model of Alexander Osterwalder and Yves Pigneur

Using this model, you can build a business model for karting.

Karting is a profitable business. It has a relatively small entry threshold, and the market is practically free. Competitors can only be found in big cities, and even then there are few. There are two lines of business:

- Entertaining karting club;
- Sports section, which prepares athletes for participation in competitions.

An entertaining karting club, according to experts, is more profitable to open. Karting for children is especially in demand.

At the heart of sports entertainment is a large area or track, which is called the "karting track". It can be covered or open. The second open-air grounds operate only in the warm season, so this karting club can be considered seasonal. Small cars that are made specifically for racing on small tracks are called "karts". They are small vehicles that do not have a body, but are capable of accelerating to high speeds.

For the construction of the route, 700 m long, you will need a land plot with an area of 3-4 thousand square meters. The road for cars should be paved with the right turns and a sufficient number of straight sections. Usually, an amateur karting or sports club is built away from residential buildings and the city center. An old production facility or an unclaimed warehouse is suitable as a covered area.

The number of staff in the club depends on their professionalism and skills. It is ideal to find such people who will understand the technique, who will be able to fix the go-karts and at the same time instruct clients. If children's karting opens, it's good that the instructors know how to get along with children. Of the additional, but mandatory attributes, you will need to purchase overalls for workers and helmets for visitors. Beautiful identical overalls of the staff will create a positive image, and corporate symbols will make it possible to recognize the club at competitions. On normal business days, the form allows attendees to quickly find a member of staff to ask for help. A quality helmet made in Italy costs about \$60, but there are also cheap Chinese options. Before laying the coating, it is desirable to equip the kart with timing. This device allows you to record the time of arrival, the results and display them

on the scoreboard. With this attribute, it will be much more interesting for the client to visit the karting club. You can arrange impromptu competitions and observe the dynamics of your own results. It will take about 80 thousand dollars to complete the arrangement of the track, with a coating and all the attributes.

Karting must be equipped with cars. A new car costs from 1.5 to 4 thousand dollars, depending on the power. The main and most expensive part of the car is the engine. Karting frames can also be bought domestically or imported. However, many amateurs and professionals make karts with their own hands. It's much cheaper and more reliable.

Before proceeding with the manufacture, you need to determine what the future karting will be like. The basis of each technical product is a drawing, according to which it is necessary to calculate the amount of necessary materials. Metal pipes are used for frames, they are cut into parts, bent and welded. After manufacturing the main frame, you can begin to design the motor frame, pedal control and steering assembly. All these parts are made according to the same scheme, but their dimensions can be adjusted depending on the height of the person who will operate the machine.

Do-it-yourself karting is equipped with a single-cylinder air-cooled gasoline unit. The pilot must be protected from internal combustion engines and possible burns. The braking system combines at least a pair of wheels.

A workshop that makes karting with their own hands, the presence of a chic track and attentive staff, all this can become a favorite vacation spot for both adults and children. It is these components that will become the key to your unique and profitable business, with a chic name - karting.

Estimates of theorists and entrepreneurs who have been earning money on karting for more than one year practically do not differ in the main indicators: profitability, the amount of starting capital, the time required to reach the level of self-sufficiency, etc. (which is quite rare in such situations). Consider the main economic results of a company operating in the industry represented:

- \$7,500 monthly income

- expenses of the enterprise, which include: staff salaries, advertising, depreciation, insurance premiums, taxes and other administrative expenses - \$ 2,400 per month.

- net profit, based on the above indicators, will be at the level of \$ 5100 / per month.

But, taking into account various force majeure, changes in the competitive situation or general economic trends, the company's profit can be \$ 2,500-6,000 per month.

For start-up capital, which is necessary to create a full-fledged company working in this direction, it is necessary to consider the implementation of the idea in question: the creation of a full-fledged karting club. The track and related infrastructure facilities are being built, the necessary equipment is being purchased, and preparatory courses for different age groups are being organized, etc. In this case, you need to invest from 700

thousand to 1 million dollars, but the exact amount depends primarily on the location of the future company.

When preparing a business plan for the implementation of this project, you definitely need to calculate the cost of the main equipment and the most "killed" spare parts (rubber, brake system, filters, etc.), as well as study in detail the cost of equipment that will help save the most valuable thing - life and the health of every person.

An example is the karting track STK "Sokol" located in the Almaty region. The Sokol STK autodrome is a large-scale project that combines a complex of unique racing tracks and entertainment. The commercial zone is open to all visitors to the autodrome. There is a hotel, food outlets, dry closets, mini golf, paintball, as well as a museum of automotive technology.

Table 5.

Business model of the Autodrome STK Sokol

Key Partners/ Suppliers: - karting clubs -suppliers of card machines; -companies with sports equipment	Key processes: - karting - leisure - entertainment	Advantages of the offer: - hotel, - food outlets - dry closets, -mini golf, -paintball, Museum of Automotive Engineering.	Customer Relations: -social network - commercials - Events -corporate parties - sport events	Target audience segments: - men - women, - children.
	Key resources: - Go-karting -Different age group - Amateurs and professionals		Communication channels: - complex - TV - social media	
Cost structure: - economic needs - Maintenance - kart repair		Sources of income: - go-kart rental - entertainment center - the price depends on the category of services		

1. Conclusion

A business model is not a business plan. Building a model does not involve deep analysis and therefore cannot be the basis for making strategic decisions. But the business model is ideal for quickly evaluating hypotheses and identifying current risks for the company.

If you take a foreign model as a basis, you can certainly create your own karting circuit for the younger generation. It is possible to gather everyone in one region, or in a large settlement, in cities, draw up a business plan, make an educational and methodological development plan, organize a material and technical base and start a business to prepare children and teenagers for karting.

The main thing in this business is to gather those who want to practice these sports, to give stability in training, diversity and gradual expansion. Significant is a stable financial base and support from both the state and charitable sponsorship. If we offer the state

as a project that supports a healthy lifestyle, and sponsors as a profitable investment, then there is a chance to develop this sport in the Republic of Kazakhstan.

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